

HETEROSIS STUDIES FOR YIELD AND YIELD CONTRIBUTING TRAITS IN LINSEED (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)V.A. Kulkarni^{1*}, P.B. Wadikar², A.R. Jadhav³ and D.D. Lathe⁴^{1,3,4}Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, COA, Latur, Maharashtra, India.²Associate Professor, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, COA, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

Ten diverse lines of linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) were crossed in line \times tester fashion to study average heterosis, heterobeltosis, and standard heterosis over the checks LSL-93 and TL-99 for seed yield and its contributing traits during Rabi, 2022-23 and evaluated in 2023-24. The experiment was carried out at the Experimental field, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Latur, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra. Among the twenty-four crosses, GS-105 \times EI-5511 showed the highest average heterosis, heterobeltosis, and standard heterosis over both checks for seed yield per plant followed by ES-1445 \times EI-5511, EC-41741 \times EI-5511, JLS-395 \times GS-09, ES-1445 \times GS-09 and EC-41741 \times RLC-04. The cross GS-105 \times EI-5511 also showed heterosis for characters viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, days to maturity, number of branches per plant, number of capsules per plant, and harvest index. Hence, the crosses having high heterosis can be effectively used for heterosis breeding or isolating transgressive segregants, which will increase the frequency of desirable genes for heterosis breeding or isolating transgressive segregants, which will increase the frequency of desirable genes for yield component traits along with economic traits in linseed.

Keywords: Linseed, Heterobeltosis, line \times tester, seed yield, standard heterosis)

Introduction

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) n=15, also called flax is an important oilseed crop grown for both seeds and fibers which belongs to the family *Linaceae* having 14 genera and over 200 species. The origin of linseed is presumed to be in southwest Asia, particularly in India. The linseed oil is rich in fatty acids alpha-linolenic acid (ALA) and lignin oligomers accounting for 57 % of total fatty acids in its biochemical composition (Mishra *et al.* 2013). The crop is predominantly self-pollinated, but outcrossing (less than 2%) occasionally results from insect activity.

It is grown during the Rabi season in India. Because it is a cool-season crop, growing conditions must be mild to cool. After mustard and rapeseed, it is the least important. Currently, Madhya Pradesh is India's top producer of linseed followed by West Bengal, Jharkhand, Bihar, Orissa, Maharashtra, Chhattisgarh, Uttar Pradesh, and Karnataka. In 2022–2023, 179.90 lakh hectares were planted with linseed, yielding an average of 671 kg of productivity per hectare and 43 metric tons of production per year. In Maharashtra, there are 39 thousand hectares of linseed planted, with an annual production of 10,000 tons and an average productivity of 246 kg per ha. In Marathwada, there are 16,000 hectares of linseed grown with an annual production of 5.2 thousand tons and the average productivity is 314 kg per ha. (Anonymous 2023). The average productivity is very low as compared to other countries where it is grown. Hence, there is an urgent need to increase productivity by breaking the present yield barrier and developing hybrids with high yield potentials.

The study on the magnitude of heterosis would help in identifying promising cross combinations for the exploitation of heterosis for genetic improvement of quantitative traits and genetic information on heterosis is useful for developing breeding strategies to meet the demand of increasing population. It is necessary to have detailed information about the desirable parent combination in any breeding program which can reflect a high degree of heterotic response. It has become a common practice of the plant breeder to work with crop plants to obtain genetic information of diverse breeding material from the line \times tester technique developed by Kempthorne (1957). Therefore, heterotic studies can provide the basis for the exploitation of valuable hybrid combinations in future breeding programs as earlier reported by Sood *et al.* (2011), Mishra (2013), Pali and Mahto (2014). The present investigation was undertaken to measure the magnitude of heterosis in hybrids for seed yield and associated traits in linseed.

Materials and Methods

The experimental material comprised six promising listed lines having higher yield and better agronomic characters viz., FR-111, GS-105, JLS-395, ES-1445, EC-41741, and Mutant-02 were crossed with four different testers having broad genetic bases and wider

adaptability viz., GS-36, LSL-93, RLC-04, and EI-5511. The 24 hybrids were raised along with respective parents in randomized block design with two replications during Rabi, 2022-23, and evaluated in 2023-24. The experiment was carried out at the Experimental field, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Latur, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra. The hybrids and parents were sown in single rows of 2-meter length with inter and intra-row spacing of 30 cm and 5 cm, respectively. All recommended agronomical packages of practices and plant protection measures were followed timely to raise a good crop.

Five plants were selected randomly in each replication from each parent and hybrid and observations were recorded for ten quantitative characters viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, number of branches per plant, number of capsules per plant, number of seeds per capsule, 1000 seed weight (g), seed yield per plant (g), harvest index (%) and oil content (%). The mean values were calculated and used for statistical analysis. The data recorded on F₁s were analyzed as per the method suggested by Kempthorne (1957). Heterosis over mid-parent, better parent, and standard checks LSL-93 and TL-99 for all the ten characters were estimated.

Results and Discussion

The statistical analysis of variance provided in Table No.1 for the averaged data examining different characters for different entries showed that treatments (parents, and crosses) were highly significant for most of the characters under investigation, suggesting a significant degree of variability in the experimental material employed in the study.

Earliness for 50 per cent flowering and days to maturity is highly desirable. The crosses exhibiting significant negative heterotic effects for this trait are considered desirable. Among 24 crosses, the cross Mutant-02 \times EI-5511 (-13.51%) manifested the highest negatively significant heterosis over mid-parent whereas, the cross GS-105 \times EI-511 (-14.81%) reported the highest negatively significant heterosis over better parent and GS-105 \times RLC-04 (7.69 %) least positively significant heterosis over the standard check LSL-93 as none of the crosses were earlier than check LSL-93. Mutant-02 \times EI-5511 (-9.68%) manifested the highest negatively significant heterosis over the mid-parent, the cross Mutant-02 \times RLC-04 (-18.52%) reported the highest negatively significant heterosis over the better parent whereas, the cross GS-105 \times RLC-04 (-2.35%) exhibited negative but non-significant heterosis over the check LSL-93 for days to maturity. Tallness in linseed is desirable. The crosses exhibiting a significant positive heterotic effect are desirable. Among crosses, JLS-395 \times LSL-93 (24.13%) exhibited the highest significant heterosis over mid-parent, the cross GS-105 \times GS-09 (8.92%) reported highly significant heterosis over better parent whereas, the cross GS-105 \times

GS-09 (90.19%) manifested highest significant heterosis over check LSL-93. For the number of branches per plant, positively significant heterosis is desirable. Cross EC-41741 × EI-5511 (101.93%), (88.89%), and (52.24%) exhibited the highest significant heterosis over mid-parent, better parent, and check LSL-93. For the character number of capsules per plant, cross EC-41741 × EI-5511 (102.62%) and (99.85%) reported the highest heterosis over mid and better parent whereas the cross JLS-395 × GS-09 (114.46%) exhibited the highest significant heterosis over check LSL-93. Among 24 crosses, ES-1445 × LSL-93 (0.88%) showed positive but non-significant heterosis over mid-parent, whereas, the cross EC-41741 × LSL-93 (-10.66%) exhibited the highest but negatively significant heterosis over better parent and cross EC-41741 × GS-09 (4.11%) recorded highest significant heterosis over check LSL-93. Crosses did not show heterosis over the better parent and check LSL-93 for the number of seeds per capsule as there is not much difference present between parents and crosses for this character.

For the character 1000 seed weight, the cross ES-1445 × RLC-04 (30.08%) reported the highest significant heterosis over mid-parent whereas, ES-1445 × LSL-93 (24.08%) manifested the highest heterosis over the better parent, and the cross ES-1445 × RLC-04 (10.37%) exhibited highest heterosis over the check LSL-93. The cross JLS-395 × GS-09 (73.10%) exhibited the highest significant heterosis over mid-parent for seed yield per plant (g) whereas, the cross EC-41741 × EI-5511 (65.42%) reported the highest significant heterosis over the better parent, and GS-105 × EI-5511 (36.71%) manifested highest significant heterosis over the check LSL-93. For the character harvest index (%), Mutant-02 × RLC-04 (20.65%) reported the highest significant heterosis over mid-parent, the cross Mutant-02 × RLC-04 (0.30%), (4.08%) manifested positive but non-significant heterosis over better parent as well as check LSL-93. Cross GS-105 × RLC-04 (14.51%), (6.41%) exhibited the highest significant heterosis over mid-parent and check LSL-93, respectively. Out of 24 crosses evaluated, six crosses and twelve crosses showed desirable significant negative heterosis over mid parent and better parent respectively. Thirteen crosses reported negatively significant heterosis over the check TL-99. Significant negative mid parent and better parent heterosis for days to 50 per cent flowering and days to maturity in linseed. The above findings are in agreement with Mishra *et al.* (2013), Kumar *et al.* (2014), and Chaudhary *et al.* (2016). All the yield-contributing characters showed positive and highly significant heterosis over the mid-parent, better parent and standard check LSL-93 as given in Table No.2 except the number of seeds per capsule and harvest index as there is not much difference present between parents and crosses for number of seeds per capsule character. When heterosis is significantly positive for these characters, the use of the heterosis breeding method is desirable. Biparental mating or recurrent selection approach is also used to develop desirable genotypes. Similar result was recorded by Sood *et al.* (2011), Kumar *et al.* (2013), Kumar *et al.* (2016), Sedhom *et al.* (2016), Dhirhi *et al.* (2018) and Rathwa *et al.* (2023).

Conclusion

Six crosses *viz.*, GS-105 × EI-5511 (41.27, 39.06 and 36.71%), ES-1445 × EI-5511 (60.38, 32.81 and 30.57 %), EC-41741 × EI-5511 (65.42, 31.56 and 29.34%), JLS-395 × GS-09 (59.92, 29.69 and 27.50%), ES-1445 × GS-09 (54.53, 27.97 and 25.81%) and EC-41741 × RLC-04 (31.36, 25.00 and 22.89%) expressed significant positive heterosis over better parent, standard check TL-99 and LSL-93, respectively for seed yield per plant. These crosses with high heterotic effect also gave an idea to consider these heterotic effects for production of superior lines. However, the isolation of superior lines may be difficult in small population of heterotic crosses in which the number of segregating loci with additive gene effect is relatively large. In such circumstances, it would be better to adopt the "Biparental mating crossing approach" for the accumulation of favourable and additive gene effects for linseed improvement (Pali and Mahto, 2014). The results of the present study indicated that the

crosses exhibited high heterotic along with high *per se* performance for seed yield and its important attributes, which might be useful in the heterosis breeding programme.

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Table No.1: Analysis of variance for parents and hybrids for ten characters in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)

* and ** indicates significance at 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively.

Sr. No.	Characters	Sources of variation			S.E. (±)
		Replication	Treatment	Error	
		d.f. (1)	d.f. (35)	d.f. (35)	
1	Days to 50 per cent flowering	5.013	45.039*	1.871	0.96
2	Days to maturity	0.222	129.5**	2.050	1.012
3	Plant height (cm)	3.845	177.4**	2.056	1.013
4	No. of branches per plant	0.435	1.031**	0.126	0.252
5	No. of capsules per plant	1.745	527.49**	17.55	2.96
6	No. seeds per capsule	0.3029	0.94**	0.09	0.211
7	1000 Seed weight (g)	0.7729	2.170**	0.19	0.307
8	Seed yield per plant (g)	0.295	0.779**	0.11	0.231
9	Harvest index (%)	8.604	63.753**	9.423	2.17
10	Oil content (%)	0.010	19.47**	0.56	0.514

Table No.2. Best heterotic crosses over mid-parent, better parents and standard check LSL-93 for ten different characters in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)

* and ** indicates significance at 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively.

Sr. No	Characters	Most heterotic cross over mid parent (%)		Heterobeltosis (%)		Standard check (%) LSL-93	
1	Days to 50 percent flowering	Mutant-02 × EI-5511	-13.51**	GS-105 × EI-5511	-14.81**	GS-105 × RLC-04	7.69*
2	Days to maturity	Mutant-02 × EI-5511	-9.68**	Mutant-02 × RLC-04	-18.52**	GS-105 × RLC-04	-2.35
3	Plant height (cm)	JLS-395 × LSL-93	24.13**	GS-105 × GS-09	8.92**	GS-105 × GS-09	90.19**
4	No. of branches per plant	EC-41741 × EI-5511	101.93**	EC-41741 × EI-5511	88.89**	EC-41741 × EI-5511	52.24**
5	No. of capsule per plant	EC-41741 × EI-5511	102.62**	EC-41741 × EI-5511	99.85**	JLS-395 × GS-09	114.46**
6	No. seeds per capsule	ES-1445 × LSL-93	0.88	EC41741 × LSL-93	-10.66**	EC-41741 × GS-09	4.11
7	1000 Seed weight (g)	ES-1445 × RLC-04	30.08**	ES-1445 × LSL-93	24.08**	ES-1445 × RLC-04	10.37*
8	Seed yield per plant (g)	JLS-395 × GS-09	73.10**	EC-41741 × EI-5511	65.42**	GS-105 × EI-5511	36.71**
9	Harvest index (%)	Mutant-02 × RLC-04	20.65*	Mutant-02 × RLC-04	0.30	Mutant-02 × RLC-04	4.08
10	Oil content (%)	GS-105 × RLC-04	14.51**	ES-1445 × EI-5511	4.64*	GS-105 × RLC-04	6.41**

Table No.3: Six best heterotic crosses and their *per se* performance for seed yield per plant and yield contributing traits in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.)

Sr. No.	Crosses	Seed yield per plant (g)	Mid parent heterosis (%)	Heterobeltosis (%)	Standard heterosis (%)		Desirable Significant positive standard heterosis
					SC-I	SC-II	
1	GS-105 × EI-5511	4.45	56.28**	41.27**	39.06**	36.71**	DFE, DM, NBPP, NCPP, HI
2	ES-1445 × EI-5511	4.25	63.62**	60.38**	32.81**	30.57**	NBPP, NCPP, TW
3	EC-41741 × EI-5511	4.20	66.90**	65.42**	31.56**	29.34**	NBPP, NCPP, HI, TW
4	JLS-395 × GS-09	4.1	73.10**	59.92**	29.69**	27.50**	NBPP, NCPP,
5	ES-1445 × GS-09	4.09	56.15**	54.53**	27.97*	25.81*	NBPP, NCPP, HI
6	EC-41741 × RLC-04	4.00	44.27**	31.36**	25.00*	22.89*	DM, PH, NBPP, NCPP, TW

* and ** indicates significance at 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively.

Whereas,

DFE - Days to 50 percent flowering

PH - Plant height (cm)

NBPP - Number of branches per plant

NCPP - Number of capsules per plant

DM - Days to maturity

NSPC - Number of seeds per capsule

HI - Harvest index (%)

TW - 1000 seeds weigh (g)

Fig No.1: Performance of best six crosses for per se performance, better parent heterosis (%), standard heterosis (%) over checks TL-99 and LSL-93.